

Speculation on Special Relativity and Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 24, 2022

$-Et + px$ is an example of a Lorentz invariant. The two 4-vectors (p, E) and (x, t) transform according to a Lorentz transformation which is linked to viewing a system from different frames moving at constant velocities v . There is, however, a second solution namely $t=C/E$ and $p=C/x$ ($C=\text{constant}$) which also keeps the inner product constant. This is not linked to frame transformations because for a given p or E one has a specific x or t value which has to be thought of in a different manner. In particular, it may represent an interval ("pocket") in space or time i.e. x as $1/p$ is a wavelength. This may also be connected with a free particle Action.

If x as $1/p$ represents an interval in space, it seems there should be a probability distribution associated with such an interval. If this is the case, the idea of Shannon's entropy should hold within that region. Thus increasing energy (and p) leads to smaller wavelength regions i.e. higher resolution. Using ideas from a bound infinite well we argue that entropy for a crest decreases as the resolution increases. Thus high energy of a constant velocity particle is linked to the idea of low entropy if one uses invariance in special relativity and utilizes a second solution which keeps $-Et+px$ constant. This approach is equivalent to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ the wavefunction of free particle. Thus the idea of entropy and its relationship to energy may be linked with both special relativity and the quantum mechanics of a free particle, something that does not seem to be evident from classical mechanics.

Lorentz Transformations

Lorentz transformations are well defined and describe four vectors such as (p, E) or (x, t) as viewed from different constant moving frames with velocity v . An example is (1)

$$X' = x/\sqrt{1-vv} - vt/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{and} \quad t' = t/\sqrt{1-vv} - vx/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((1))$$

As a result, one may have a Lorentz invariant or dot product e.g. $-Et+px$

$$-E't' + p'x' = -Et+px \quad \text{using} \quad ((1)) \quad ((2))$$

Second Solution for Lorentz Invariant

There is a second way to maintain invariance of $-Et+px$ without using ((1)) namely to use:

$$x=C/p \quad \text{and} \quad t= C/E \quad \text{where } C \text{ is a constant} \quad ((1))$$

This is unusual, however, because it considers a fixed length C/p associated with a constant p . A particle moving with a constant speed does not have an associated fixed length in classical mechanics. One may, however, suggest that actual motion, even constant, is complicated (not merely a translation) and that there may be an inherent cycling effect associated with $t=C/E$ and a cycling length of C/p . Experiments (e.g. two slit interference, single slit diffraction, bound state

humps) seem to confirm this. Thus using a second solution to create a Lorentz invariant seems to lead to “pockets” of space and time. This suggests there may be associated probability densities. For example if there is a fixed length C/p and the particle is within such a region, then its probability is zero to be outside the region.

Classical Action

If one takes the classical action for a free particle (relativistic $A = -m_0 c t \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$) or (nonrelativistic $t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$) and writes $v=x/t$, then varying x and t independently yields:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((3))$$

This leads to $-Et+px = A$ which is a Lorentz invariant. As argued in previous notes (2) one may create eigenvalue equations which seem to represent a kind of dynamical or cycling probability:

$$-i\partial/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ and } i\partial/dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((4))$$

This, however, is consistent with ((1)) i.e. $p=2\pi/\text{wavelength}$ and $E = 2\pi/\text{frequency}$. In this case, the probability distribution discussed above is explicit, namely $\exp(ipx)$. We have argued in previous notes that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent two distributions marking the presence of the particle within wavelength regions, but are shifted and show dynamics. In particular the negative part of $\cos(px)$ shows that probability disappears in a wavelike manner, but appears in $\sin(px)$ which is the shifted distribution. The main point we wish to stress is that there is a distribution of the form of $\cos(px)$ representing crests and troughs marking the “pocket” of length i.e. the wavelength. $\exp(ipx)$ has modulus 1 so one may argue that it is the modulus which represents $P(x)$.

Nevertheless we argue that the crests of $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ are important as they are linked to entropy.

The Idea of Entropy

In the above sections we argued that relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions of a free particle are of the form $A = -Et+px$. This is a Lorentz invariant and a second solution to maintaining a constant, other than a Lorentz transformation, is to have $t=C/E$ and $p=C/x$. This is consistent with eigenvalue equations ((4)) which use $\exp(iA)$.

If one considers an infinite well (0 to L) one may use $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ or $C\sin(px)$ as a linear combination such that $p=3.14 n / L$. Squaring $C\sin(px)$ yields $P(x)$ a probability distribution. We argue that each hump represents its own spatial probability distribution and should thus be associated with its own Shannon’s entropy. This entropy applies to the crest linked to the “special length” C/p i.e. it is half a wavelength. The spatial entropy overall does not change as n increases, but there are n humps, so the entropy of each hump is constant/ n . Thus entropy per hump drops and resolution increases with an increase in energy. This is very different from classical mechanics where one does not really consider entropy unless one has heat production or an ideal gas. A classical particle moving at a constant speed would not be

considered to have a different entropy than one moving with a slower speed, but the quantum humps seem to indicate this. Furthermore not only are there pockets in space, but as one adds energy, the entropy of the pocket decreases as its resolution increases (size becomes smaller).

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that a free particle classical action $A = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant and is thus linked to special relativity. A solution to A constant, other than a Lorentz transformation, is $t = C/E$ and $p = C/x$. This is unusual, however, because it suggests pockets of time and space. One may use A to establish eigenvalue equations with x and t independent (the exact opposite approach of classical mechanics. This leads to $\exp(-iA)$ as a solution which reinforces $t = C/E$ and $p = C/x$. It seems that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are linked to shifted probability distributions in space. $P(x)$ is given by the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$, but this is $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px)$ i.e. two shifted distributions are used. If one considers a particle in an infinite well at $(0, L)$ then $C\sin(p\text{ave } x)$ is a solution where $p = 3.14 n/L$. Squaring $C\sin(p\text{ave } x)$ gives a set of humps. We argue that each is a probability distribution linked to the pocket of space C/p . Thus one may calculate Shannon's entropy for a hump. The overall Shannon's spatial entropy $-\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ is independent of n , i.e. a constant, but each n has n humps so the entropy per hump is constant/ n . Thus increasing energy of a free particle not only increases resolution, but lowers entropy per hump. Thus the idea of entropy is already present in the quantum mechanical description of a free particle (moving at a constant velocity) we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lorentz_transformation
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)